

CLARIN Annual Conference Proceedings

2025

Edited by

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30 September – 2 October 2025
Vienna, Austria

Please cite as:
CLARIN Annual Conference Proceedings, 2025. ISSN 2773-2177 (online).
Eds. Cristina Grisot and Thalassia Kontino.
Vienna, Austria, 2025.

Building IcePInt: The Icelandic Parliament Interviews corpus

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Abstract

We describe ongoing work constructing a corpus of interviews with Icelandic Members of Parliament. IcePInt, the Icelandic Parliament Interview Corpus, is currently being used to augment data from the Icelandic Parliament Corpus for a project that analyzes Icelandic political speech. It is an argument for doing such work in Iceland that Icelandic politicians are more approachable by researchers than politicians in larger language communities. We are able to carry out linguistic interviews with current and former MPs, including high-ranking ministers.

1 Introduction

We describe work in progress on building a novel CLARIN resource, a corpus of interviews with Icelandic Members of Parliament (MPs). This effort is a part of the ERC-funded project Explaining Individual Lifespan Change (EILisCh). The EILisCh project involves analyzing speeches from the Icelandic parliament and tracking changes over time in how individual MPs as well as entire political parties use certain linguistic features. This primary analysis uses the Icelandic Parliament Corpus, a subset of the Icelandic Gigaword Corpus, but in order to interpret linguistic lifespan change of individual politicians, a better understanding of their career and attitudes is needed. This is where the Icelandic Parliament Interview corpus, IcePInt, comes into play. IcePInt involves directly interviewing current and former Icelandic MPs, recording the interviews both in terms of audio and video, transcribing them, and using them for analysis. Thus, while the analysis of the parliament speeches yields quantitative analysis of how the speech of the MPs evolved over time, IcePInt adds qualitative detail that allows us to interpret the quantitative findings. This new interview corpus will then be released under a Creative Commons Attribution license at the end of the project, facilitating its use in a variety of future projects.

Stefánsdóttir and Ingason (2018) carried out a study which in some respects is a pilot study for the EILisCh project. In their analysis, they track the use of Stylistic Fronting (SF) (Thráinsson, 2007), a word order phenomenon that indexes formality, in the speech of Steingrímur J. Sigfússon, a former MP and former finance minister. They also interviewed Sigfússon and their analysis connects the evolution of SF in his speeches with events in his history that are discussed in the interview, such as the economic crisis of 2008, after which he became finance minister. The creation of IcePInt allows us to apply a similar approach of combining quantitative and qualitative findings, but on a much larger scale.

The paper is organized as follows: Section 2 provides some background for our paper, Section 3 describes the interviews that make up the contents of the corpus. In Section 4 we discuss the publication of the corpus in open access via CLARIN and Section 5 concludes this paper.

2 Background

The EILisCh project is a five year project, aiming to use data on political speech to study individual lifespan change. As mentioned, the core quantitative analysis focuses on parliament speeches from the Icelandic Gigaword Corpus (Steingrímsson et al., 2018), using automatic annotation in order to extract tokens of interesting variables which are then coded both automatically and semi-automatically and

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Figure 1: Our interview setup: In this case, one of the authors, Lilja Björk Stefánsdóttir, is interviewing Geir Haarde, a former MP who was the prime minister of Iceland during the economic crash of 2008.

analyzed further (Stefánsdóttir & Ingason, 2018). It has also been verified that the automatic coding of the primary variable, SF, is accurate enough to be used for analysis even without manual correction (Stefánsdóttir & Ingason, 2025).

Although there are not many other interview corpora for Icelandic, some previous projects compiled and made use of conversation data, which is similar to our data in some respects. To mention some examples, work by Hilmisdóttir (2024), who has examined conversations of young Icelanders in relation to their use of Anglicisms. Furthermore, Gísladóttir (2015) has studied repair strategies in Icelandic conversations. Despite these and various other efforts, there is a clear need for Icelandic interview corpora with audio and video that are annotated and published in open access. Note that in an international context, numerous studies of interviews and conversations have made use of similar data sources, for example, Fu and Ho (2022) on TV interviews and Oertel et al. (2014) who developed a multi-modal corpus for analyzing conversational behavior in group interviews. While the development of open access corpora for Icelandic specifically is a field that needs to be established further, our contribution is a step towards such work.

3 The Interviews

The most unique aspect of the IcePInt corpus is that the EILisCh project makes use of the small size of the Icelandic language community in order to get access to the most prominent national politicians as candidates for linguistic interviews. We are certain that it would be much more challenging to approach a number of former MPs, some of whom have been ministers, in a large language community where high-profile politicians are less approachable.

Our interview setting can be seen in Figure 1. In this case, one of the authors, Lilja Björk Stefánsdóttir, is interviewing Geir Haarde, a former MP who was the prime minister of Iceland during the economic crash of 2008. We are grateful for the participation of such prominent politicians in our project.

The interview structure is designed around a series of questions with possible follow-ups. We first give out information about the study, then we ask the participant about their background and family. Next we transition into a phase where we focus on the parliament, asking about what drove the person to go into politics and run for parliament and we also ask about their career in the context of how they felt about being in this workplace. We also pose questions about the Icelandic language, their views on the language in general and what they think about the use of Icelandic in the parliament setting. Because we

are interested in the evolution of their careers, we acquire information about events or periods that the participant experienced as particularly challenging, and how these affected them. We give our informants the opportunity to add anything that they may find relevant and finally, we show them a graph of how we measure their level of formality over the years (as in Stefánsdóttir & Ingason, 2018), and directly confront them with our findings, allowing for a discussion of what may have affected changes in their linguistic behavior. Each interview is about one hour in length.

For all interviews, we record video in 4K resolution on a Sony A7S III camera, and for the audio, we always use two independent recordings for redundancy.¹ The primary audio recording mechanism is a pair of wireless Sony microphones connected to the camera and attached to the interviewer and the participant, but we also have an Audio-Technica microphone on the table to capture backup audio (see Figure 1). All videos are edited to start at the beginning of the first question and end once the final discussion ends.

The audio and video are imported into ELAN for transcription (Sloetjes & Wittenburg, 2008). The primary use of the annotation for us is to be able to extract quotes that shed light on how the career and attitudes of the participant shed light on the evolution of their linguistic behavior. For this reason, our transcription is very simple: We transcribe all the words that are said manually, including repetitions and disfluencies that involve speaking words, but we do not write down non-word disfluencies or coughs or the like. This strikes a balance between using our resources primarily for our current project while constructing a resource that can be used for other purposes, possibly with further annotation. We note that discourse markers such as *heyrðu* ‘well’ (Jónsdóttir & Gísladóttir, 2025) are transcribed and can therefore be studied in the data.

Although it is not clear at this point how many politicians will accept our invitation in the project, we have already carried out thirteen interviews and continue to schedule further ones in order to grow the size of the corpus. We plan to add a substantial number of interviews until the end of the project in 2028. It should be noted that all participants sign an informed consent form that allows for publication of the data in open access.

4 Publication

While the data collection is ongoing, the data will remain closed. But before the end of the project, the entire corpus, video, audio, and transcriptions, will be released and made available through the CLARIN infrastructure. We will not release the data immediately because we aim to do the first analysis of the data within our project and because we want the corpus to be complete before releasing it. While we reserve the rights to use the corpus while the project is ongoing, it is possible that we will collaborate with members outside the project group during this period, but we do remain committed to an open access policy so that all the data will eventually be released with a Creative Commons Attribution license (the CC BY). Our lab has a good track record in this respect, having released various previous resources on CLARIN, such as the Icelandic Error Corpus (Arnardóttir et al., 2021) and IceTaboo, a database of contextually inappropriate words in Icelandic (Sólmundsdóttir et al., 2021).

Also, while the initial goal of the data collection is to shed light on linguistic lifespan change of Icelandic politicians, the nature of the data makes it suitable to studying various other topics. The interview data could be used for other linguistic topics such as discourse analysis, but also for studying phenomena beyond linguistics such as political history. In any case, the eventual publication of this corpus in open access via the CLARIN framework will facilitate future work that may make use of this resource in diverse ways.

5 Conclusion

In this paper, we have described ongoing work constructing a corpus of interviews with Icelandic politicians that will be released in open access via CLARIN when it is completed. This corpus project is connected with a larger project that aims to analyze linguistic lifespan change of Icelandic politicians by studying their parliament speeches, but the present corpus will lead to more qualitative depth by asking

¹An exception is the first couple of interviews which were recorded in 1080p resolution.

Icelandic politicians directly about their personal histories and attitudes. A central argument for carrying out work of this type in Iceland is that in such a small language community, local celebrities such as prominent politicians are more approachable than in other larger communities. But it is also important in general to study a wide range of languages and work on lifespan change has been relatively biased to focus on English; including Icelandic in the range of languages being examined for lifespan change is therefore an important goal of our work.

Acknowledgments

This project is supported by a grant from the European Research Council (ERC), project ID 101117824. Thanks, as well, to the participants in the study who volunteered their time to be interviewed for the project.

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